

The Implementation of Learning Model in Talking Stick by Using Short Story Text to Improve Students' Reading Comprehension At SMP Negeri 15 TIKEP

Lisnawati Harun
English Education Program, STKIP Kie Raha Ternate

Abstract

This Research is a class act that uses short story text thorough learning model of talking stick to improve students' reading comprehension. This subject is class VII SMP NEGERI 15 Tidore Kepulauan 2017-2018 school year the sample of 12 students. This study to be implemented in one class, each cycle consisting of four components, namely: planning, implementation, observation, and reflection. Data were collected through taking video, observation sheet and field note on each cycle. Based on the results of research, teaching by using short story text through learning model of talking stick can improving students' reading comprehension of the students class VII SMP NEGERI 15 TIKEP. The results of the research subjects to study of reading and understanding the meaning of short story text on the actions of the first cycle still there are 6 students who do not achieve mastery, while 6 other students have achieved mastery. In the second cycle action, and from 12 students who following the learning, all of them achieved mastery. Which means all of students in the second cycle have completed if the value measured by KKM 70.

Keywords: *Learning Model of Talking Stick, Short Story Text, Students' Reading Comprehension*

© Langua – 2018

1. Background

In teaching learning process, there is a learning model that must to be used to achieve the purpose of learning. That is why a learning model is so important. So, the definition of the learning model is a manner that used to implementation the plan that has been prepared in the form of real and practical to achieve the learning. The various kinds of learning model that can be used to implement learning strategies, one of which is the learning model talking stick.

Every learning model that is used a teacher in learning, its purpose to realize the purpose of a learning, this learning model is not only used a teacher to increase the students' speaking ability but also can increase the students' reading comprehension.

But usually, so many problems are found in reading, For example, when reading one or two page with the writing is full but no one idea that is obtained from the reading, because while reading our minds are not focus or difficult to concentrate, but our eyes keep looking the text that we are reading, this is because writing in the text is not interesting, until the activity reading be an

boring activity. Therefore, the students are lazy, so the students' reading comprehension is so weak. But there is also that makes the reading activity be an gratify activity, it is when we read short story. Because short story is a piece of prose fiction that can be read in one sitting, in the short story there are orientation, complication, climax and resolution, of these characteristics can make the reader wants to understand the meaning of text. So, therefore the researcher improves students' reading comprehension by using short story text through learning model of talking stick at SMP NEGERI 15 TIKEP.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Reading Comprehension

According to Wooley (2011:15) Reading comprehension is the process of making meaning from text. The goal, therefore, is to gain an overall understanding of what is described in the text rather than to obtain meaning from isolated words or sentences.

According Peter Westwood (2008: 32) Reading comprehension is often conceptualized as functioning at different levels of sophistication and referred to, for example, as literal, inferential and critical. The most basic level (literal) is where the reader is able to understand the factual information presented in a passage of text – for example, he or she can tell you the name of the main character and what he does for a living, because that information is stated explicitly in the text. The next level is referred to as the inferential level.

According Van den Brooek & Espin, (2012) Reading comprehension is a complex interaction among automatic and strategic cognitive processes that enables the reader to create a mental representation of the text.

According Van Dijk and Kintsch (1983) defined reading comprehension as the process of creating meaning from text. The purpose is to get an understanding of the text rather than to acquire meaning from individual words or sentences.

So, from the definitions above, the researcher concludes that reading is an important activity that must to be improved. Because, with the reading, the reader can get information that want to found, but to get the information the reader must to understand the meaning of the text. Therefore, the reader must to focus when reading.

2.2. Strategy of Reading Comprehension

According to Mc Namara, (2007: p.6-9) reading comprehension strategy is a cognitive or behavioral action that is enacted under particular contextual conditions, with the goal of improving some aspect of comprehension.

Some strategies are related to bottom-up procedures, and others to enhance the top-down processes. The strategies for reading comprehension are:

- a. Identify the purpose in reading
- b. Use graphemic rules and patterns to aid in bottom-up decoding (for beginning level learners)
- c. Use efficient silent reading techniques for relatively rapid comprehension (for intermediate to advanced levels)
- d. Skimming
- e. Scanning
- f. Using semantic mapping or clustering
- g. Guessing
- h. Analyzing Vocabulary
- i. Distinguishing between literal and implied meaning
- j. Capitalizing on discourse markers to process relationship

So, the researcher concludes that the strategy of reading comprehension is a manner for making each reader easy to understand the meaning of a text.

2.3. Learning Model of Talking Stick

The learning model of talking stick is a model of group learning with the help of a stick, the group that is holding the stick must answer the questions of the teacher after they learn the main subject (read the content of the text that is given by the teacher), then the activity is repeated until all groups get a turn to answer questions from the teacher.

According to Sudjana (2001:10) Learning model of talking stick is a learning model that use tool in the form of a stick as a tool for teacher is asking questions to students by raising nice atmosphere. The stick is rolled over to the students and if a student who get the stick then the student will be given questions by the teacher and must be answered.

Shoimin (2014) says that the Talking Stick is a method that was originally used by Native Americans to invite everyone to speak or express an opinion in a forum (meeting tribe) using a stick.

According to Knockwood (1992), in Mi'kmaw culture, Talking stick is a piece of wood used in Talking Stick Ceremony. Anyone with the talking stick would have the right to talk as long as

they need to say without fear of being interrupted with question, criticism or scolding. Hence it becomes signifier democracy. In OSLC classroom, the talking stick can be any ordinary stick of any kind or any size. Whoever has the talking stick has the right to talk, and else would keep silent and listen.

This learning model is done with the help of a cane, who holds the stick must answer questions from the teacher after the students learn the subject matter. "Learning stick talk is very suitable for elementary students because in addition to training in speaking, this learning will make it more fun and make students active" (Kharis and Rakhmawati, 2014)

The learning model of Talking Stick is very suitable applied for elementary, junior high and high school. In addition to training in speaking, this learning also can improve the student's reading comprehension and will create a fun atmosphere and makes students active.

According to Nanang Hanafiah and Suhana (2012: 48) The steps of its application can be done as follows.

1. The teacher forms some groups in the class that made up of 5 or 6 members.
2. The teacher prepares a stick that is 20 cm in length.
3. The teacher delivers the subject that will be learned, then gives the opportunity to groups to read and study the subject matter.
4. After finished reading the subject matter and learning the content, the teacher ask the students to close the book.
5. The teacher takes the stick and gives to one of the group members, after that, the teacher gives the questions and the group members that is holding the stick must answer it, and continue to another students also get question by the teacher and answer it.
6. Other students may help answer the questions if the group members can not answer the questions.
7. The teacher gives a conclusion.
8. The teacher makes the evaluation / assessment, in groups or individual.
9. Closing

2.4. Advantages and Disadvantages the Learning Model of Talking Stick

The learning model of talking stick according to Sugeng (2011: 1) has advantages such as:

- a. Testing students' readiness,
- b. Practice reading and understanding quickly,
- c. To be more active in learning.

The advantages of using learning model of Talking Stick to test the readiness of students in receiving learning, making students read and understand the lesson quickly and make students more study hard, so it is expected can improve students' achievement (Suprijono, 2009).

From the opinions above, can be concluded that the learning model has advantages as follows:

1. Students are directly involved in learning activities
2. There is an interaction between teachers and students
3. Students become more independent
4. Learning activitie is more fun

In every learning model, if there are advantages. Then, of course there are also disadvantage, the disadvantage is make students who are not ready to be nervous when they get the stick and answer question from the teacher.

But, the disadvantage can be coped with various motivations and support from a teacher.

2.5. Short Story

A short story is one that is meant to be read in one setting. Typically, a short story ranges from 2000 to 7500 words in length. Short story is less complex than novels, often focusing on a single incident. They have a small number of characters. As with short-short story, short stories may have a surprise ending.

There are some definitions of short story according to several experts:

“A crucial feature commonly identified with the short story is its impression of unity since it can be read-in contrast to the novel-in one sitting without interruption. Due to restriction of length, the plot of the short story has to be highly selective, entailing an idiosyncratic temporal dimension that usually focuses on one central moment of action.” (Klarer, 1998:14)

So, the researcher concludes that short story is a fictional essay that contains about the life of a person and focused on a character only.

2.6. Characteristics of short story

- The plot of story is shorter than the novel
- A short story has total word that no more than 10.000 words
- Usually the story content comes from daily life
- Does not describe all the stories of the characters, this is because in the short story that is described only the essence.
- The character in the short story is described as having a problem or a conflict until the completion stage.

- The use of simple words and economical and easily known by the reader.
- The impression left behind from the story is so profound that readers can sensed the plot of the story
- Usually, only one event is told
- Characterization in the short story is very simple, not deep and short.

3. Method

This research is a classroom action research. According Burns (Through Madya, 2007:8), action research is the application of the discovery of facts in solving problems in social situations with a view to improving the quality of the action performed in it, which involves collaboration and cooperation of the researchers, practitioner, and lay people. This design is used for know the students' action in the class. So, this research procedure is in accordance with classroom action research procedure, that is done in a cyclic process.

Every cycle consists of planning, action, observation and reflection. This is in accordance with the opinion of Kemmis S. and M.C. Taggart (1988), which states that classroom action research is a spiral self-reflection cycle to make improvements process to existing conditions, find solutions to solve problems and find new manner of better and more effective to achieve more optimal results.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Finding

This chapter will describe the data and finding of each phase of the research action within each cycle from the planning, action, observation and reflection. Data presented in the cycle of one and then will be discussed in the discussion of research. Results from the analysis of reflection and discussion on cycle are used as a reference in the planning and implementation of the next cycle. There were two cycles, the first cycle consisted of two meetings, and the second cycle consisted of two meetings.

4.1.1. Cycle I

From the evaluation result of students learning in the first cycle, the students overall cannot yet reach KKM. From 12 students and after implementation the learning model of talking stick by using short story text but reached KKM scored only 6 students, while the other six received grades below 70 which means it does not reach the KKM . it can be seen in the table below:

Table 4.1.1 Scoring Rubric

No	Names	Result Score	Maximal Score	Students' Value
1	Riswan Masri	9	12	75
2	Arfandi Muhdar	8	12	67
3	M Rafik Sama	6	12	50
4	Sakinah M Noh	10	12	83,3
5	Fitria Usman	10	12	83,3
6	Nurfalah Abdullah	10	12	83,3
7	M Saleh Muhdar	6	12	50
8	Nurjani Safrudin	8	12	67
9	Wildayanti Umar	10	12	83,3
10	Musri M Hi Abas	7	12	58,3
11	Nurmayanti E Surare	10	12	83,3
12	Usman Saleh	3	12	25

$$\frac{\text{Result Score}}{\text{Maximal Score}} \times 100\%$$

= Student's Value

Based on the table above can be seen that the students who have the highest score or reach KKM in understanding the meaning of short story text are 83,3 obtained by five students, 75 obtained by one student, and who got low grades or not reach KKM in understanding the meaning of short story text are 67 obtained by two students, 58,3 obtained by one student, 50 obtained by two students, and 25 obtained by one students, because the student was absent at the second meeting.

And that becomes problems until some students have not been able to reach the target of KKM is the problems that written by collaborator in field not.

4.1.2. Cycle II

From the evaluation result of the students' learning in the second cycle, the problems above did not affect the enthusiasm of students to understanding the content of the text. So, can be concluded that learning model of talking stick by using short story text achieve good improvement. From 12 students following study reading short story text, all of them gained the

value reached KKM. Which means all of students have completed if the value measured by KKM “70”. It can be seen in the table below:

Table 4.1.2 Scoring Rubric

No	Names	Result Score	Maximal Score	Students' Value
1	Nurfala Abdullah	10	12	83,3
2	Sakinah M Noh	10	12	83,3
3	Nurmayanti E Surure	9	12	75
4	Usman Saleh	9	12	75
5	Wildayanti Umar	11	12	92
6	M Rafik Sama	10	12	83,3
7	M Sale Muhdar	9	12	75
8	Musri M Hi Abas	9	12	75
9	Fitria Usman	11	12	92
10	Nurjani Safrudin	9	12	75
11	Riswan Masri	10	12	83,3
12	Arfandi Muhdar	9	12	75

$$\frac{\text{Result Score}}{\text{maximal Score}} \times 100 \% = \text{Student's Value}$$

Based on the table above can be seen that the students who have the highest score or reach KKM in understanding the meaning of short story text are, 92 obtained by two students, 83,3 obtained by four students, 75 obtained by six students,.

4.1.3. Overall Finding

Comparison of the evaluation result are shown in table 4.1 and 4.2 above shows the acquisition value of the students during classroom action research cycles carried out. It appears that the increased student scores in each cycle being held. Based on the acquisition value of the individual student appears that some students in pre-cycles there were 4 students who reached KKM while 8 others have not yet reached KKM, it is because there is not motivated in learning. So, students feel boring and lazy to understand the meaning of text although the teacher had given students opportunity to open dictionary. The first cycle there were 6 students who have achieved

KKM while the other 6 have not achieved KKM, (1) some students have not been able to answered all questions from the teacher because the time was given by teacher is lack. So that the text was understood by students is limited or not whole, but when the students are asked by teacher, they answered have finish. (2) Lack of teacher in controlling the activities of students in work, causing students focus more on other things. Some were playing, and there were also joking with friends. It also makes teacher did not know the difficulties of students so when students need directive, no directing. But on the second cycle the students' learning outcomes increased and of 12 students could reach KKM. This means that increase in students' reading comprehension by using short story text trough learning model of talking stick is success. From the comparison of each cycle in this research, the researcher presented in Table 4.2.2 as follows:

Table 4.2 The Comparison Value Of Students Each Cycle

Name Of Students	Comparison Value		
	Pre-cycle	Cycle I	Cycle II
Arfandi Muhdar	67	67	75
Fitria Usman	79	83,3	92
M. Saleh Muhdar	66	50	75
Musri M Hi Abas	59	58,3	75
M Rafik Sama	63	50	83,3
Nurfalah Abdullah	77	83,3	83,3
Nurjani Safrudin	65	67	75
Nurmayanti E Surure	69	83,3	83,3
Riswan Masri	80	75	83,3
Sakinah M Noh	67	83,3	92
Usman Saleh	69	25	75
Wildayanti Umar	77	83,3	92
Total	838	808.8	967.2
Average	69.83	55.6	80

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1. Teaching and Learning in reading a text by using short story text through learning model of talking stick

The use of short story text through learning model of talking stick can enhance students'. Increasing students' attention because this learning model is a new learning model that used in the class VII SMP NEGERI 15 TIKEP, with the formation of groups and with the help of a stick obliges the students to answer these questions when holding the stick, this motivate the students try to understand the meaning of the text because each student does not want when his turn is holding the stick he cannot answer the questions that asked by the teacher related with content of the short story. And in the every short story there are interesting pictures, with the interesting

pictures also can invite students' curious about the meaning of the text. So, the short story text and the learning model of talking can be applied to the reading material as well as understand the meaning of reading text.

4.2.2. *The Improvement of the Students' Reading Comprehension*

In the learning process of reading short story text, the students in the class VI a have improved very well. It is found from the research results pre-cycle where in each cycle artifacts good improvement of each student with a number of 21 students. Starting from pre-cycle, there were 4 students have met the KKM and 8 others have not met the KKM, then in the first cycle of students who have met the KKM increased to 6 students and 6 others have not met the KKM, even the value of the 4 students decreased. while in the second cycle, all of students reached KKM. So this research has ended in the second cycle.

From the comparison student learning outcomes in a cycle that has been carried out. Any assessment criteria assessed by scoring rubric reading can be depicted on the graph as follows:

Chart 4.2.2 Graph the increase of students from each

From the graph above it can be seen that any improved and also decreased in the first cycle but in the second cycle the all of students achieved the KKM. For pre-cycle with the students' average total reach 69, 83 with presentation 33.33%. This is can be seen from the students' value at the first semester. And then cycle I with the students' average total decreased 55, 6 with presentation 50 %. This is because there is a student who did not follow the learning (absent). Meanwhile on the cycle II the students' averages improve 80 with the presentation 100%. Until to cycle II students have success.

5. Conclusion

In this research can be concluded that to improve students' reading comprehension by using short story text through learning model of talking stick then it must to follow the steps such as below:

1. The teacher asks the students to form 3 groups, and every group made up of 4 members.
2. After making the groups, the teacher then ask one of each group to choose their title of short story.
3. After the students chose, the teacher then stuck the picture on the white board about the story of each group. This makes the students more enthusiasm to study.
4. The teacher gives the short story text to every group in accordance with the title they have chosen.
5. Before the students are asked to read, the teacher explain to the students about the learning model that will be used, that is the learning model of talking stick and then explain the rule of the learning model. The rule is the students who hold the stick must to speak.
6. The teacher gives 40 minutes to students read and understand the content of text, and ensure some students must take the English dictionary
7. The teacher always controlling every work of group, and if find difficulties in a group then the teacher gives direction to overcome it.
8. After reading, the teacher hold a stick and gives to a student, and after the student answer the questions then the teacher gives the stick to other friends to answer the next questions. Always like that until all of the students get the turn and answer the next questions
9. The teacher gives a conclusion.
10. The teacher makes the evaluation / assessment, in groups or individual.
11. Closing

This is based the opinion of Nanang Hanafiah and Suhana (2012: 48) the steps of its application can be done as follows.

1. The teacher forms some groups in the class that made up of 5 or 6 members.
2. The teacher prepares a stick that is 20 cm in length.
3. The teacher delivers the subject that will be learned, then gives the opportunity to groups to read and study the subject matter.
4. After finished reading the subject matter and learning the content, the teacher ask the students to close the book.

5. The teacher takes the stick and gives to one of the group members, after that, the teacher gives the questions and the group members that is holding the stick must answer it, and continue to another students also get question by the teacher and answer it.
6. Other students may help answer the questions if the group members can not answer the questions.
7. The teacher gives a conclusion.
8. The teacher makes the evaluation / assessment, in groups or individual.
9. Closing

And at the second cycle in this research, all off students follow the steps above “all the students that holding the stick have spoken (answered the questions).

To know the improvement based on the result of data that got through video, observation sheet and field note.

1. The Pre-cycle, the students overall have not yet reached KKM. With a description of the number of students who achieve complete value just 4 students and 8 other students have not reached the value completely.
2. Through the learning model of talking stick by using short story text that seen on the first cycle has not yet reached complete learn. The descriptions of the number of students who achieve complete value are 6 students and 6 others have not yet reached the KKM, even the value of some students decreased.
3. In the second cycle, all of students can reached the KKM, even more the KKM.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Armbruster Bonnie B, 2000. Put Reading First: the Research Building Blocks for Teaching, (*Third Education, USA, National Institute for Literacy*),
- Brooek Van den, P., & Espin, C.A, 2012. Connecting cognitive theory and assessment: Measuring individual differences in reading comprehension. *School Psychology Review*.
Deakin University.
- Dijk Van, & Kintsch, 1983. *Strategies of discourse comprehension*. New York: Academic Press.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1461445606059565>
- Grabe, W. 2009. *Reading in a second language (Moving from theory to practice)*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Hanafiah Nanang dan Suhana 2012. *Konsep Strategi Pembelajaran*. Refika Aditama: Bandung.
- Kemmis, Mc Taggart, (1988). *The Action Research Planner, (third ed.)*. Victoria:
- Kharis & Rakhmawati, 2014. *Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Talking Stick untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Siswa pada Materi Pelajaran Teknik Elektronika di SMK Negeri 7 Surabaya*. Jurnal Pendidikan Teknik Elektro,
- Klarer, 1998. *Introduction to Literary Studies*. London:Routledge
- Knockwood. 1992. *One Space Learning Circle and Active Learning in English Communication Class*.
<http://www.terrydean.org/7>
- Kruidenier, Jhon. Ed.D. 2002. *Research-Based principles for Adult Basic*
- Kurniasih Imas and Sani Berlin, 2015. *Ragam pengembangan model pembelajaran*. Yogyakarta: kata pena
- Madya, 2007. *Penelitian Tindakan Kelas*. Jakarta: Erlangga
- Namara Mc,Danielle S.2006. *Reading Comprehension Strategy*.
Pearson Education Canada Inc, 2005. Permission to reproduce this page is restricted to the purchasing school
- Shoimin, 2014. *Model Pembelajaran Inovatif dalam Kurikulum*. Yogyakarta: Ar-ruzz Media.
- Sudjana. 2001. *Metode dan teknik pembelajaran partisipatif*. Bandung : Falah Production
- Sugeng 2011. <http://abdulgopuroke.blogspot.co.id/2017/03/model-pembelajaran-talking-stick.html?m=1> (diakses pada 16 februari 2017)
- Westwood Peter, 2008. *What Teachers Need to know about reading and writing difficulties*, First Edition, Australia, Acer Press
- Wooley, G. (2011) *Reading Comprehension:Assisting Children with Learning Difficulties*. New York: Springer